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Megalithism and new research perspectives on argentiferous galena mines of Bric Gettina (Rialto, near Finale Ligure – Western Liguria)

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This paper analyzes the ancient mining site, its location, orientation, relationship with adjacent structures of archaeological and archaeoastronomical interest that could be related to a pre-and/or protohistoric frequentation of the place and the resulting new research perspectives.

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Summary

The Authors analyse the ancient mining site, its location, orientation, relationship with adjacent structures of archaeological and archaeoastronomical interest that could be related to pre-and/or protohistoric frequentation of the place and the resulting new study opportunities.

Description

Bric Gettina, also called Purin in Ligurian language (because from its eastern slopes originates Pora river or Porrino or Purin, which gives its name to the homonymous valley), placed between Bric della Guardia (in the north) and Rocca Cucca (located to the south of Gettina itself) is, with these mountains, a watershed between the Maremola Valley to the west and the Pora Valley to the east. The mines are located on the eastern side of Bric Gettina, then in upper Pora Valley, in the territory of Rialto, north of Finale Ligure (Savona Province, Western Liguria). It can be reached along a path that starts near “Osteria Vecchia” (or “Osteria of the Din”), crosses “Cà del Mago”, goes around the southern top of Purin and descends at an altitude of 882 m asl.

GPS coordinates, obtained on a "table" of stone, supported by smaller rocks facing the entrance of tunnels, are: Latitude: 44.22552°North, Longitude: 8.22887°East.

Photo 1

The path (Figure 1) is of an enchanting beauty and you can enjoy a magnificent view over Pora Valley and Finalese, with the pleasant surprise that, even at the level of the mining site, the Authors were able to observe, although in late September, the splendid flowering of *Campanula Isophylla* (19), typical of limestone rocks of Finalese, also between the slits of Melogno porphyroids (Photo 2).

Figure 1

Photo 2

The trail is not marked. It branches off from the main path, at about 1200 m. from “Osteria Vecchia”, upstream, at an acute angle, barely visible to the hiker and goes slightly uphill to the east around the top of Bric Gettina, then winding down on Pora Valley side. The distance can be completed in an hour. A dwell on panoramic point, consisting of the culmination of an extensive and high ridge, overlooking this Valley, lets you see the rugged southern slope of the mountain, which has gullies overgrown. The track goes down, then, on sections supported by high stone walls, ancient but solid, walking on particularly steep tracts. Because of the narrowness and high grass, you need to pay constant attention to support points of the march. At level of the mines, you can

enter, cautiously, armed with a flashlight. The tunnels are dug into solid rock without any support: failures and collapses are possible.

The first written record of these mines date back to 1453, by the humanist Giovanni Mario Filelfo (Constantinople, Pera 1426 - Mantua 1480) in his "Bellum Finariense" of 1453 (Filelfo, G. M. "La Guerra del Finale" 1447-1452"), a chronicle of the war waged by the Genoese against Del Carretto Marquisate (16).

Along with the history of this war event, he also gives news about people who worked as "Argentari" (i.e.: silver miners) in the mountains near Finale Ligure. Mines were exploited mainly from the fifteenth to the seventeenth century.

From the geological viewpoint, the prevailing formation is made up by Melogno porphyroids. These are metamorphic rocks (which has undergone transformations linked to high temperatures and high pressures), effusive, of volcanic origin (Geological Age: Lower Permian or Cisuralian: from 299.0 ± 0.8 to 270.6 ± 0.7 million of years ago), composed of rhyolites (quartz and feldspar, the latter minerals are in laminar structure) and rhyodacites (compact rocks, from pink to purple and also green). It comes to observation, for the most part, as a green rock, if the surface is fresh, or brown if the surface is altered, finely schistose, with millimetric bands, alternately whitish and greenish, with few phenocrystals (i.e.: visible crystals, because of their size, larger and well distinguishable from the surrounding rock matrix), less than a centimeter, of quartz with potassium feldspar.

On this geological substratum, the tunnels of the Bric Gettina Mines were dug.

By the end of the eighteenth century, had begun their decline, and, finally, abandoned and forgotten in the early twentieth century, also for visible cryoclastic phenomena that deeply infringe the overlying rocks, making them unsafe (18), (27).

Quite recently were rediscovered and today are destination of fascinating excursions (19) and, although devoid of extraction interest, maintain a very important possibility of finding minerals (2) the, in addition to Galena (Lead Sulfide, which can contain from 0.05% to 0.7% of Silver), as well as:

- ◆ Allanite (containing Cerium, a Rare Earth);
- ◆ Aurichalcite (Zinc and Copper Hydroxide Carbonate);
- ◆ Cerussite (Lead Carbonate);
- ◆ Hemimorphite (containing Zinc and Silicium);
- ◆ Massicot (Lead Oxide);
- ◆ Pyromorphite (Lead Chlorophosphate);
- ◆ Smithsonite (Zinc Carbonate, used for the extraction of Zinc);
- ◆ Blenda or Sphalerite (Zinc and Iron Sulfide, used for industrial production of Zinc);
- ◆ Wulfenite (Lead and Molybdenum Oxide, rare enough, used for the extraction of Molybdenum);
- ◆ Zincite (Zinc and Manganese Oxide).

Of great interest is, above all, Archaeological profile that is represented by the ancient mining site consisting of five tunnels, the longest of which is about 70 meters (Photo 3).

Entrances, which are located along a straight line, from north to south, of about 100 meters, were opened on mineralized quartz veins guide, discontinuous, which stopped to a short distance from origins. The mined ores, were cleaned on site and the waste was collected in the aforementioned landfill (in Italian is called "Ravaneto"), located near the mines (Photo 4).

The gangue containing the argentiferous galena, was brought to the valley along the steep paths of the mountain. Then, the extracted materials were crushed with a mallet, driven by a water mill, to separate it from the gangue (19).

Photo 3

Photo 4

The ore was first melted between 950 and 1200°C, in reducing atmosphere, so that all the Silver passed in the Lead. The operation could be conducted in a vertical shaft kiln whose charge, introduced from above, was made up of charcoal mixed with the mineral. The continuous operation

of bellows allowed to maintain the high, necessary, heat. The end result was the slag, which was eliminated, and the argentiferous lead.

Then, by cupellation (this term comes from the “cupels”, the crucible commonly used in the Middle Ages, but already known in ancient times), the Silver was separated from Lead by oxidation: the metal obtained was, in fact, an association of Lead, Silver and other elements (such as Gold, Copper, Zinc, Antimony, Arsenic and Bismuth). Then it was again submitted to melting at about 1000°C, this time, however, in the presence of air, blown with bellows into the furnace, which oxidized the Lead, producing Litharge (Lead Oxide). This compound also adsorbed the oxides of the other metals, except Silver and Gold, which were, thereby, available (28).

The Litharge constituted, furthermore, the raw material for the production of Lead that was remelted in a reducing environment (the melting point of Litharge is 880°C) at times, in the same furnaces just described. The end result was a Lead, at 98-99%, poor of silver (50-200 g/t), but with significant impurities (around 1 to 2% of Copper, Antimony, and Arsenic) that made it rather hard (13), (14).

Discussion

It is assumed that the interest for silver obtained from the mines of Bric Gettina, may have been justified by the value held by this metal (similar to the value of gold in ancient and medieval times), although present in relatively small amount.

The presence, in the immediate vicinity, of stone building ruins (Photo 5) and of a structure (also in stone), similar to “Caselle” (i.e.: little cabins of stones) of Western Liguria (Photo 6), is suggestive of a possible attendance of the analysed places in earlier times respect to those now commonly considered.

Photo 5

The finding, also, of two large stones oriented to the north (Photo 7 and Photo 8) (Altitude: 951 m asl, Lat.: 44.22380°N, Long.: 8.22854°E) and of a dolmen appearance artifact (Photo 9 and Photo 10) (Altitude: 940 m asl, Lat.: 44.22457°N, Long.: 8.22839°E), together with the already described stone table, recall the megalithic structure of Finalese stone altars (4), (5), (6), (7), (8), (9), (10), (11), (17), typical of Celtic-Ligurian cultures, dating back to a period from the end of the fifth, to the end of the third millennium BC: timeframe comprising the Neolithic and Bronze Age (12), (13),

(14), (15), (20), which suggests a possible knowledge of places that can be traced back to this time span (21), (22), (23), (24), (25), (26).

Photo 6

Photo 7

Photo 8

Photo 9

Photo 10

Photo 11

The discovery of another Dolmen-like building with an adjacent Menhir (also oriented to the north, Altitude: 913 m asl, Lat.: 44.21935°N, Long.: 8.22788°E) (Photo 11 and Photo 12) and the remains of a presumed Neviera (i.e.: Ice House) (Altitude: 908 m asl, Lat.: 44.22017°N, Long.: 8.22788°E) (Photo 13), in the vicinity of Bric Gettina, would further strengthen this hypothesis.

Photo 12

Photo 13

Recent studies, based on the new methods of ICP/OES or AAS (acronyms for Induced Coupled Plasma/Optical Emission Spectroscopy and Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy) demonstrated that the metallurgy of silver, which is closely associated with Lead metalworking, was already practiced

in Liguria from the Middle Bronze Age (1600 - 1350 BC) and the local mining was also well-known in adjacent Bormida Valley, especially for Copper (13), (14).

These latest technologies, become an integral part of archaeometallurgy and archaeometry, allowed to revise the thesis, now obsolete, that Ligurians did not have a prehistoric metallurgical activity of its own, but had to import metal artifacts with trade and/or plunder.

Liguria and especially the West with Finalese, was, therefore, since the Bronze Age, the route for metal exchanges, between Mediterranean Sea, Northern Italy and Central Europe (13).

Conclusions

From the presented data it is possible that Bric Gettina Mines were part of a mining network with nearby Bormida Valley and remaining Western Liguria and that the site, given the megalithic evidences, even archaeoastronomical oriented, found in the immediate vicinity, was already known in prehistoric period (Neolithic and Bronze Age).

This hypothesis could be further supported by desirable archaeometric investigations on materials found in the site, with the help of additional new archaeometallurgical techniques available.

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